

Glycolate Complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III)

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The formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of rare earth ions ($M^{3+} = La^{3+}, Ce^{3+}, Pr^{3+}, Nd^{3+}, Sm^{3+}, Gd^{3+}, Dy^{3+}, Ho^{3+}, Er^{3+}, Tm^{3+}, Yb^{3+}$ and Lu^{3+}) with glycolic acid (HG) have been studied *pH* metrically. The equilibrium constants for the reactions

MOELLER¹ has reviewed the rare earth complexes. Some attempts have been made on the structural study²⁻³ and on the determination of thermodynamic functions⁴ of the rare earth glycolates. The present communication reports the formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 rare earth glycolate complexes by *pH* measurement method.

Experimental

The rare earth nitrates (99.99% pure) were obtained from the Indian Rare Earth Ltd. and Research Organic/Inorganic Chemical Corporation, U.S.A. *pH* titrations were performed at $32 \pm 1^\circ$ with a digital *pH* meter (ECI-Model 822A) in nitrogen atmosphere after maintaining an ionic strength of 0.1M by the addition of potassium nitrate.

Results and Discussion

Determination of formation constants of 1 : 1 complexes :

The reaction taking place due to the interaction of the rare earth ions with glycolic acid can be represented as :

where C is the complex formed and n is the number of protons liberated per gm atom of the rare earth metal ions. The values of n are calculated by the method followed in the cadmium citrate complex⁵ and gluconate complexes of yttrium⁶, praseodymium, and neodymium⁷, samarium, gadolinium, dysprosium and holmium⁸ using the equation

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - a/b \Delta[TG]}{[C]} = n - a/b \quad \dots (2)$$

where $a = \frac{k}{[H^+]}$ and $b = 1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}$ and *pk* for glycolic

acid⁹ is 3.71. $\Delta[NaOH]$, and $\Delta[TG]$ are the difference in the molar concentrations of sodium hydroxide and total glycolate at two points on the same axis of curves B and A. [C] and [M] represent the molar concentrations of the complex and metal salt respectively.

Fig.1 0.1M NaOH added ml.

Fig. 1. *pH* titration of 50.00 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g mole of potassium nitrate and 3.125×10^{-4} g. mole of glycolic acid (Curve A) and that of same volume of twelve other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of rare earth nitrate against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide. B₁ - La(III), B₂ - Ce(III), B₃ - Pr(III), B₄ - Nd(III), B₅ - Sm(III), B₆ - Gd(III), B₇ - Dy(III), B₈ - Ho(III), B₉ - Er(III), B₁₀ - Tm(III), B₁₁ - Yb(III) and B₁₂ - Lu(III).

When the formation of the complex is complete

$$[C] = [\text{Metal salt}]$$

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{TG}]}{[\text{Metal salt}]} = n - a/b$$

The values of n are more than one beyond pH 4.6, 4.6, 4.4, 4.4, 4.4, 4.6, 4.2, 4.2, 4.2, 3.8, 3.8 and 3.6 respectively for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) respectively. Below these pH values the reaction (1) may be represented as

$$\text{and } K = \frac{[C^{2+}][H^+]}{[M^{3+}][HG]} \quad \dots (4)$$

Assuming n to be one below these pH values, $[C^{2+}]$ is calculated. $[M^{3+}]$ is obtained by subtracting $[C^{2+}]$ from $[M(\text{NO}_3)_3]$.

The negative logarithm values of the equilibrium constants, K , were calculated by the equation (4) and the values with the standard deviation are 1.58 ± 0.03 , 1.37 ± 0.06 , 1.17 ± 0.10 , 0.94 ± 0.05 , 0.87 ± 0.07 , 1.19 ± 0.05 , 0.75 ± 0.12 , 0.67 ± 0.14 , 0.63 ± 0.06 , 0.38 ± 0.10 , 0.32 ± 0.11 and 0.17 ± 0.04 , respectively for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems.

In the pH ranges, 4.8-6.8, 4.8-6.4, 4.6-6.65, 4.6-6.9, 4.4-6.8, 4.6-7.0, 4.4-6.45, 4.4-6.3, 4.4-6.0, 4.0-6.56, 4.0-6.33 and 3.8-6.05 for the above systems La(III)-Lu(III) respectively, n is >1 but <2 . Hence in the pH ranges, the complex, C^{2+} , dissociates to C^+ and a proton

It can be shown as before that

$$K_1 = \frac{[C^+][H^+]}{[C^{2+}]} = \frac{(n-1)[H^+]}{(2-n)} \quad \dots (6)$$

The $-\log K_1$ values calculated by the equation (6) are found to be 6.64 ± 0.17 , 6.38 ± 0.08 , 6.36 ± 0.22 , 6.25 ± 0.16 , 6.01 ± 0.15 , 6.34 ± 0.06 , 5.89 ± 0.12 , 5.76 ± 0.12 , 5.70 ± 0.09 , 5.55 ± 0.09 , 5.40 ± 0.04 and 5.14 ± 0.10 for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively. The hydroxide of the metals are precipitated at pH , 6.60, 6.40, 6.65, 6.90, 6.80, 7.00, 6.45, 6.30, 6.0, 6.56, 6.33 and 6.05 respectively for La(III)-Lu(III) systems.

Determination of formation constants of the 1 : 2 rare earth glycolate complexes :

The reaction taking place in the formation of 1 : 2 glycolate complexes can be represented as

Fig. 2. pH titration of 50.00 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate and 5.65×10^{-4} g. mole of glycolic acid (Curve-A) and that of same volume of twelve other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of rare earth nitrate against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide. B_1 - La(III), B_2 - Ce(III), B_3 - Pr(III), B_4 - Nd(III), B_5 - Sm(III), B_6 - Gd(III), B_7 - Dy(III), B_8 - Ho(III), B_9 - Er(III), B_{10} - Tm(III), B_{11} - Yb(III) and B_{12} - Lu(III).

The values of n were calculated by the equation (8).

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{TG}]}{[M(\text{NO}_3)_3]} = n - 2a/b \quad \dots (8)$$

Above pH 4.6, 4.6, 4.4, 4.4, 4.6, 4.6, 4.6, 4.4, 4.2, 4.0, 4.0 and 3.8 for the above systems La(III)-Lu(III), respectively the value of n is greater than 2. Below these pH values the reaction (7) may be represented as

and

$$K^* = \frac{[C_{1:2}^+][H^+]^2}{[M^{3+}][HG]^2}$$

Assuming the value of n to be 2 below these pH values, the $-\log K^*$ values were calculated and are found to be 2.56 ± 0.06 , 2.29 ± 0.07 , 2.14 ± 0.09 , 2.09 ± 0.09 , 2.05 ± 0.06 , 2.43 ± 0.09 , 2.22 ± 0.10 , 2.10 ± 0.05 , 1.90 ± 0.05 , 1.64 ± 0.05 , 1.59 ± 0.05 , and 1.33 ± 0.03 for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively.

In the pH ranges, 4.8-6.6, 4.8-6.4, 4.6-6.65, 4.6-6.9, 4.8-6.8, 4.8-7.0, 4.8-6.45, 4.6-6.3, 4.4-6.0, 4.2-6.56, 4.2-6.33 and 4.0-6.05 systems respectively the n values are >2 but <3 . So in these pH ranges the complex, $C_{1:2}^+$ dissociates to $C_{1:2}$ and H^+ according to the reaction (10).

and

$$K_1^* = \frac{[C_{1:2}][H^+]}{[C_{1:2}^+]}$$

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The $-\log K_1^*$ values calculated as before are found to be 6.26 ± 0.10 , 5.95 ± 0.04 , 5.80 ± 0.07 , 5.78 ± 0.08 , 5.74 ± 0.04 , 6.08 ± 0.07 , 5.71 ± 0.05 , 5.70 ± 0.06 , 5.61 ± 0.16 , 5.48 ± 0.12 , 5.36 ± 0.07 and 5.23 ± 0.10 for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively. The relative order of stabilities is as expected.

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